

Nigeria's Healthcare System:

Assessing the Present and Planning the Future

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ABSTRACT

The healthcare system is fundamental to ensuring the health and prosperity of a nation. In this context, the Abuja Declaration of 2001 aimed to establish a comprehensive healthcare framework in Nigeria, promising coverage for all regions, including remote, rural, and urban areas. This ambitious plan led to the development of primary healthcare centers and state and federal teaching hospitals. However, the effectiveness of these institutions was short-lived. The Nigerian healthcare system has since deteriorated significantly due to chronic deficiencies such as government neglect, corruption, inadequate financing, non-payment of health workers, medical tourism, brain drain, and disunity among healthcare professionals. This paper examines these critical issues and proposes enduring solutions to address Nigeria's multifaceted healthcare challenges. Implementing these solutions could restore the Nigerian healthcare system to its former prominence.

Keywords: Healthcare System, Nigeria, Abuja Declaration, Corruption, Brain Drain, Medical Tourism, Primary Healthcare

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From time immemorial, the idea of immortality has captivated many. Humanity has sought various ways to prolong life, recognizing that good health is the foundation for any great undertaking and societal development. The artery of any society that must prosper is a functional healthcare system, which involves the organization of people, institutions, and resources to deliver quality healthcare services that meet the health needs of a population. Every minute, an African child dies from malaria, a preventable and curable disease, and the prevalence of terminal illnesses, such as cancer, continues to skyrocket at an alarming pace. Thus, it has become evident that the intervention of a quality healthcare system is the only solution.

The World Health Organization (WHO) has long emphasized that healthcare is a fundamental right for every human being, regardless of race, age, gender, belief, or status. In line with this, various countries have taken steps to create or prioritize their healthcare systems. In 2001, the African Union member countries, including Nigeria, gathered in Abuja to make a significant commitment—known as the Abuja Declaration—

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pledging to allocate 15% of their annual budget to improve the health sector.

In Nigeria, the government responded by formulating a national health policy that formed the bedrock of the country's healthcare system. This system was decentralized across three levels, aligned with the three tiers of government. At the local level, we have the Primary Healthcare Centers (PHCs), which are closest to the people and are meant to serve as the first point of contact for health issues. At the state level, the ministries of health oversee state teaching hospitals and provide technical support to PHCs. While at the federal level, the Ministry of Health is responsible for creating national health policies and supervising federal teaching hospitals, medical centers, and national laboratories. Ideally, teaching hospitals should only receive referrals from the PHCs.

Although this healthcare organogram appeared fascinating, its practical impact has barely been felt in Nigeria today. This is because little to no action was taken after the Abuja Declaration – it remained an impressive structure only on paper. The lack of follow-through on the Abuja Declaration is one of the reasons for the gross decay of the Nigerian healthcare system.

Seventeen years after the Abuja Declaration in 2001, the World Health Organization (WHO) ranked the Nigerian healthcare system 187th out of 190 in 2018. Unfortunately, there has not been much improvement since then. This ranking starkly indicates that Nigeria's

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well-conceived healthcare framework has derailed, with catastrophic consequences.

Picture this: you pick up a Nigerian newspaper in the early hours of a bright Monday morning, and the headlines scream at you in bold letters —

"Lack of bed spaces: Patients sleep on the bare floor and battle mosquitoes in teaching hospitals";

"Surgery by candlelight: Hospitals crippled by power outages and staff shortages";

"Resident doctors on indefinite strike due to unpaid salaries."

The ugly news goes on, underscoring the fact that the Nigerian healthcare system is besieged by numerous challenges, including the gross neglect by government representatives, inadequate budget allocations far below the agreed 15%, and widespread corruption, where both foreign and domestic funds are misappropriated. All leading to the incessant strikes by health workers and consequently, the untimely deaths of patients who were left unattended. Furthermore, outdated policies and the existence of inactive departments have further enabled the gross mismanagement of available resources.

During the tenure of Professor Eytayo Lambo, a health economist who served as the Minister of Health (2003-2007), significant reforms were made, including the establishment of PHCs. Unfortunately, today, many of

these centers are now abandoned buildings occupied by plants and animals, and characterized by fallen windows, roofs and walls, all due to poor financing and neglect. The shortage of skilled workers, lack of infrastructure, medical and surgical supplies, nonpayment of health workers, poorly funded medical schools, harsh laws that deter the private sector from investing in health, and poor medical research and development all hinder healthcare delivery.

As a result, many Nigerians, particularly the poor, dread falling sick because they know that sickness means further impoverishment due to the lack of healthcare insurance that can cover the health expenses of a patient. Thus, they turn to herbalists and native doctors instead. Currently, the health insurance scheme in Nigeria is mostly for the formal sectors e.g., the civil servants, while the informal sector that includes; market women, mechanics, street sellers etc. do not have any insurance cover—unprotected.

Then came the "Japa" syndrome – an unspoken agenda of abandoning Africa. The rate of brain drain, where healthcare professionals leave the country for opportunities abroad, is alarming. This exodus has left Nigeria with a severely inadequate healthcare workforce. Meanwhile, the situation is exacerbated by politicians and elites who engage in medical tourism, often traveling abroad for even minor treatments, such as to fix a tooth.

The disunity among healthcare workers—doctors, nurses, laboratory scientists, and pharmacists—has further

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weakened the system, as they pursue their demands independently rather than as a united front. This fragmentation allows the government to micromanage the sector, which negatively impacts patient care.

Additionally, the adage "*Nothing is free, not even in Freetown*" seems to elude many African leaders, who often display an overdependence on foreign funding. This reliance is problematic because such funds can be withdrawn at any time, and donor priorities may not align with Nigeria's national policies. This raises concerns about their willingness to support initiatives like the gay rights bill, which could conflict with the interests of foreign donors. It is time for Nigeria to believe in its own capabilities and harness its potential—beggars have no place in the corridors of respect.

Unlike the manufacturing sector, where errors can be corrected by removing or remodifying defective products, errors in the healthcare system often lead to human death, which is devastating. To optimize the Nigerian healthcare system and ensure it effectively serves the people, several measures must be implemented. These include: increasing healthcare funding to meet the Abuja Declaration's commitment; ensuring continuity in healthcare leadership; combating corruption that leads to the embezzlement and misappropriation of funds; reviewing policies and establishing surveillance systems to monitor their implementation; and revitalizing and expanding

primary healthcare centers to alleviate the burden on secondary and tertiary hospitals.

The health insurance scheme should extend to everyone, not just civil servants, accommodating both the formal and informal sectors. The ministries of health need to tailor policies to make healthcare affordable, accessible, sustainable, and of high quality. A ban on medical tourism should be considered, and telemedicine could be utilized to bridge gaps between healthcare professionals and prevent professional isolation. Strategic public-private partnerships should be established, encouraging private sector investment in healthcare through incentives such as tax breaks and duty waivers on medical equipment imports.

Healthcare workers should be paid adequately and promptly, which would help reverse brain drain and restore patients' confidence in the healthcare system, thus expanding the pool of human resources. Infrastructure at all levels of the healthcare system must be revamped, and public awareness should be raised to guide individuals on where to seek specialized medical treatments, such as orthopedic or open-heart surgery. Additionally, the leadership model of the healthcare sector should be reformed to foster greater development. This could include appointing a health economist to manage health funds and a public health administrator to oversee the managerial aspects of healthcare systems, rather than having all health sector affairs led by a medical doctor.

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With effective leadership, there would be no abandoned projects, preventive medicine would be promoted, and the disunity and fragmentation among healthcare workers would be eliminated, fostering greater cooperation. Additionally, it is crucial to recognize that the scope of healthcare extends beyond diagnosis and clinical practice. Medical research and the training of medical students must be prioritized to drive innovation in the healthcare sector and increase the number of doctors and other healthcare professionals. This is essential to improving the current doctor-to-patient ratio in Nigeria, which stands at 1:5000, towards the WHO-recommended ratio of 1:600.

In conclusion, Nigeria's future would be bleak if the healthcare system remains neglected. A functional healthcare system is vital for the nation's development and economic growth. A healthy population is essential for building a strong economy. Without a robust healthcare system, Nigeria risks perpetuating a cycle of poor health and underdevelopment, while other nations that prioritize effective healthcare systems continue to prosper.

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